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The Owning of Public Space: The Impact of Play on Urban Public Spaces in the Frankenberger Neighbourhood

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Abstract

Play is commonly recognized as a creative and productive activity that fosters a child's innovative potential. However, its significance extends beyond childhood; it serves as a critical commentary on the consumption and rationality prevalent in contemporary urban life. Playful activities often manifest as spontaneous and voluntary actions, serving as a means for individuals to assert ownership over space. This ownership isn't defined by specific, written, and negotiated regulatory systems but rather by the ability of city residents to access and transform spaces through their lived experiences in the city. It represents a fusion of playful actions, creating spaces for both use and production that transcend the privatization of urban areas.

This research explores the interaction between play theory and urban design in shaping inclusive public spaces and addressing issues related to space privatization. With a focus on community involvement, particularly through participatory design approaches, it aims to align spaces with diverse needs, as exemplified by public spaces in the Frankenberger Neighbourhood in Aachen. Through observations and surveys, the study aims to illustrate how playful design fosters unique connections between people and places, thereby revitalizing public areas. The research advocates for the integration of play into design processes to inspire communal contribution, promote playfulness, encourage social engagement, and cultivate a deeper sense of ownership over space.

Keywords: Play Theory, Urban Design, Public Space Privatization, Participation, Ownership of Space

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1. Introduction

Public spaces hold a central role in urban environments, where individuals express their unique identities, foster a sense of belonging, and engage actively with their fellow citizens. However, a growing concern emerges as these communal areas increasingly transform into private domains, relegating individuals to the role of passive spectators rather than active participants (Jacobs, 1961; Putnam, 2000). This shift towards passivity has led to reduced citizen involvement and a weakening of the communal fabric within these shared spaces. In response, the concept of play theory emerges as a promising avenue to reinvigorate public engagement in both the design and use of these spaces (Sutton-Smith, 1997).

Rooted in human nature, the concept of play offers an escape from the demands of modern urban life, providing a sense of freedom for sensory and physical well-being while nurturing personal growth through social interactions (Huizinga, 1955; Caillois, 2001). Play is a dual phenomenon, serving both as an individual pursuit and a communal activity, contributing not only to personal development but also to the intricate social dynamics of urban life. In parallel, the notion of public spaces is founded on the principle of universal accessibility for all city residents, regardless of socio-economic backgrounds (Lim, 2009). Simultaneously, play theory offers a means through which individuals can actively engage with public spaces, fostering a deeper sense of participation and connection within the urban environment.

This article delves into the essential role of play in urban public spaces (Whyte, 1980). It goes beyond merely examining this concept, advocating for community involvement in the design of these spaces. Such engagement not only cultivates a sense of ownership but also fosters collective responsibility for community well-being (Hester, 2006). Through the lens of play theory, the article explores definitions that emphasize active participation in the use and design of public spaces, highlighting how play can enhance these participatory elements.

This article explores the transformative power of play in public spaces, focusing on the Frankenberger Neighbourhood in Aachen. Play is recognized not only as a creative and productive activity that fosters innovation in children but also as a critical commentary on the consumption and rationality of contemporary urban life. Playful activities, which are spontaneous and voluntary, enable individuals to assert ownership over spaces through their lived experiences rather than through regulated systems. This study emphasizes how play can create inclusive, engaging, and transformative public environments through direct observations and behaviour mapping in Frankenberger Park, illustrating the ways in which residents interact with and transform their surroundings.

The primary goal of this article is to address the challenge of encouraging active participation in public spaces by incorporating play theory into urban design. Through observations and surveys in the Frankenberger Neighbourhood, we illustrate how playful design fosters unique connections between people and places, revitalizing public areas. By integrating participatory design approaches that align spaces with diverse community needs, we advocate for a holistic approach to tackling the privatization of urban areas. This exploration underscores the importance of play in building vibrant, inclusive cities that promote social engagement and a deeper sense of ownership over public spaces. The following sections delve deeper into these

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themes, offering both theoretical insights and practical examples to demonstrate the effectiveness of play in enhancing the character of public spaces.

2. Reclaiming the Public Realm: Addressing Privatization and Enhancing Ownership

Public spaces are essential conduits in cities, acting as channels through which the vibrancy of urban life flows, enriching the social, economic, cultural, and political fabric of communities. However, these vital areas are currently facing a significant challenge: the trend towards privatization and its effects on public engagement and a sense of ownership. This shift has led to users becoming passive participants in the management and design processes, diminishing their active engagement and ownership of these spaces. To address these issues effectively, it is imperative to first establish a clear and comprehensive definition of what public spaces should embody, setting the stage for a deeper exploration of their current challenges and then potential solutions by play theory.

In contemporary urban environments, public spaces are increasingly diverging from their democratic ideals as forums for sharing, confronting differences, and expressing ideas. A fundamental problem underpinning this shift is the growing trend of privatization. In many cities, the streets once solely managed by local governments are now being matched by the emergence of private, managed spaces. During this era of neoliberalism, privatization has led to the establishment of design rules by city planners, notably in cities like New York and London, aiming for open and varied public use. However, this often results in public areas that lack a sense of ownership and belonging. The takeover of urban life by private interests is a gradual process, leading to a practical, but restrictive approach to managing and protecting public spaces (Carmona, 2022).

The rise of neoliberalism has accelerated the privatization process within urban landscapes, advocating for enhanced entrepreneurial liberties in a context shaped by individual autonomy, the sanctity of private property, open markets, and the facilitation of free trade (Harvey, 1989). This process is transforming public spaces, once vibrant hubs of civic engagement and community interaction, into commercialized areas focused on consumption. The privatization of public spaces often leads to a reduction in active, participatory opportunities for the public (Harvey, 1989). As public spaces become increasingly privatized, the tapestry of our social life risks unravelling, as uniform commercial interests replace the vibrant mosaic of diverse community interactions (Smith, 2018). It has simplified public spaces, reducing them to utilitarian walkways for pedestrians and venues for consumer activities. In doing so, it has eroded their essential role as dynamic hubs for fostering a sense of ownership and belonging (Zukin, 1995). Urban designers are actively addressing this challenge, striving to create interactive and inclusive spaces that counteract the commercial forces at play (Madanipour, 2003).

Continuing from the historical perspective where public spaces were integral to urban social life, Ali Madanipour's insights delve deeper into the repercussions of their transformation in recent decades. He observes that, in the post-1980s period, these spaces have undergone significant changes, becoming more regulated and restricted as opposed to the open and inclusive designs that characterized them in the past (Madanipour, 2010). This shift toward

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control and constraint aligns with the interests of private developers, who, driven by the motive to protect their investments, have been instrumental in the privatization of public spaces. Such privatization has led to an alarming trend where public spaces are at risk of being morphed into privatized domains. The implications of this shift are profound, as they not only limit free movement but also threaten the very foundations of democracy, including the ideals of freedom and equality that public spaces are meant to uphold. He is critical of the way in which market forces have redefined the public realm, not just in physical terms but also in the social and symbolic dimensions of public life. The resulting spaces are often exclusionary, favouring consumers over citizens, and prioritize economic transactions over social interactions. This change reflects a broader societal shift where the values of the marketplace overshadow communal values, thereby diminishing the public's sense of ownership and participation that is fundamental to the vitality and identity of urban centres. Madanipour's work underscores the need for a critical re-examination of urban policy and design strategies to ensure that public spaces remain true to their purpose as democratic forums that are open and accessible to all, fostering a robust and participatory urban life (Madanipour, 2010).

Richard Sennett argues that such privatization undermines the civic and social function of public spaces, diminishing the rich, spontaneous, and often unscripted interactions that characterize a vibrant public realm (Sennett, 1977). Sennett emphasizes that public spaces should facilitate the mixing of diverse populations, allowing for the unexpected encounters that are vital for the health of a democratic society. The move towards privatization, according to Sennett, often leads to a 'tyranny of intimacy,' where public life is reduced to behaviours and interactions that are more suitable for private, controlled environments. This transition can create sterile, homogenized spaces that limit individual expression and reduce the potential for the kind of challenging and robust public discourse essential for a healthy democracy (Sennett, 1990). For Sennett, the solution lies in embracing the discomfort and unpredictability of public life, encouraging a design of public spaces that supports a sense of ownership and belonging, which are necessary for fostering stronger communal ties and a more resilient public culture.

Considering these challenges, a pivotal question emerges: How can individuals influence and contribute to the design of public spaces? The process of managing and designing involves freely using these spaces and actively making choices about their use, without the imposition of authority. How can we render these spaces more dynamic and interactive? Promoting playful actions and performances could be the key to revitalizing these areas. The article aims to shift focus toward an examination of play theory, highlighting the significance of active involvement and fresh perspectives in the design of public spaces.

3. Play Theory: Fostering Ownership and Active Participation in Urban Spaces

In the face of escalating privatization, the pressing challenge in urban design is to create public spaces that resist being overtaken by private interests and maintain their status as communal assets. These spaces should cultivate a sense of belonging and encourage active participation and ownership, standing in contrast to environments that promote passive consumption (Soja, 1996). It's within this context that play activities become essential, serving as a catalyst for participation, personal connection, and ownership of the space. To understand the

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transformative power of play in urban spaces, we must first explore the fundamental question: What is play?

Play is often seen as a creative and productive activity that fosters a child's innovative potential. However, it is not limited to children; rather, it is a voluntary engagement that individuals undertake throughout their lives in various spaces and times. The foundational work on play comes from the Dutch historian Johan Huizinga, who introduced his work "Homo Ludens" in 1938. Huizinga explores the historical significance of play, asserting that it played a crucial role in the emergence of culture. He conceptualizes human beings as "Homo Ludens" or playing humans, suggesting that actions performed in social life serve to produce the essential needs and requirements of life, thereby fostering a sense of ownership and active participation. Huizinga characterizes early human societies' life-sustaining activities, such as building shelters, hunting, and gathering, as acts of play. As human beings started creating their reality, they initially shaped everything in a rhythm, arrangement, and repetition. In essence, reality emerges as a product of playful social interactions (Huizinga, 1995).

Another defining aspect of play is its inherently fictional nature, evolving into a structured system characterized by rhythm and repetition over time. Governed by specific rules, albeit subject to change, this system operates on the principle of voluntarism, promoting active engagement and a sense of ownership over the activity. Bernard Suits emphasizes the importance of rules in the understanding of play. He stresses that the violation of these rules is prohibited, while adhering to the rules and making minor modifications can add significant value to the play. Despite the uncertainty of the outcome, Suits argues that the rules of play can be pre-determined, even if they are subject to change during play. Suits asserts that play is not simply a casual or trivial activity, but it can be defined as "doing what one wants to do" (Suits, 1978).

Caillois (1961) suggests that all forms of playful activities can be evaluated on a spectrum ranging between two fundamental aspects: *paidia* and *ludus*. *Paidia* encompasses spontaneous and improvisational actions that offer a departure from daily routines and foster active participation and a sense of ownership. It involves exploring alternative social interactions and fostering the emergence of novel social structures. Picture the playful actions of children as a prime example of *paidia*; they engage without self-awareness in their emotions and behaviours. Interestingly, adults also show a liking for unstructured behaviour and embracing risks. On the other hand, *ludus* refers to play that has been formalized into structured games. This type of play adheres to predetermined rules and established routines, often intentionally designed to be intricate and somewhat arbitrary. *Ludus*, essentially, embodies a "secondary and gratuitous" pursuit—an activity undertaken purely for the joy it brings, promoting ownership and active participation. It serves as a counterbalance to the impact of routine, monotonous work on one's sense of self (Caillois, 1961). By encouraging individuals to engage deeply and personally with public spaces, both *paidia* and *ludus* help foster a sense of ownership. This sense of ownership, in turn, leads to more vibrant and inclusive urban environments where community members feel connected and invested.

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4. Methodology

This research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining GIS mapping, on-site observation, and photography to analyse playful behaviours in urban spaces. The study focuses on two public spaces in the Frankenberger Neighbourhood, Aachen: Frankenberger Park and Neumarkt. Conducted from June to July 2023, between 4-5 pm, the observations aimed to capture a diverse range of behaviours and social interactions during hot weather conditions in the afternoons.

GIS mapping was utilized to conduct a systematic spatial analysis and visualization of playful behaviours within the selected public spaces. By collecting and analysing spatial data, this method identified spatial patterns and hotspots of playful activities, offering a spatial dimension to the understanding of play in urban environments. On-site observations were conducted to document playful behaviours, social interactions, and activities, following the principles of behavioural mapping (Ittelson, 1970). Structured observations recorded the dynamic nature of play, focusing on the types and contexts of interactions occurring in the spaces. Photography complemented these methods by capturing visual evidence and contextual information, providing a visual record of the behaviours and the spatial context in which they occurred.

Qualitative analysis was conducted by coding and categorizing the observed behaviours to identify themes and patterns, offering a detailed examination of the nature and dynamics of play in the urban context. To ensure the reliability and validity of the findings, triangulation was employed by cross-referencing observational data with GIS mapping and photographic evidence, allowing for a comprehensive analysis and verification of identified patterns. Building on the methodological framework established by Goličnik (2005), behavioural maps were used as a key tool for place analysis and design, linking spatial features with observed behaviours in both time and space. By employing these methodologies, this study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of how playful behaviours shape and transform public spaces in the Frankenberger Neighbourhood, offering insights into the integration of play in urban design to foster inclusive and engaging environments.

5. Case Studies: Frankenberger Park and Neumarkt

Frankenberger Park and Neumarkt are two prominent public spaces located in the Frankenberger Neighbourhood in Aachen, a vibrant and diverse area renowned for its rich mix of building functions. This neighbourhood, situated close to the city centre and adjacent to the Aachen ring, includes notable landmarks such as Frankenberg Castle, a former water castle now serving as a museum and cultural centre. The area predominantly houses middle-class residents and students, and it features a variety of amenities, including schools, restaurants, cafes, bookshops, markets, and museums. The presence of numerous cultural facilities, along with a large indoor concert hall, adds to the neighbourhood's dynamic character, making it a hub for social and cultural activities. This diverse urban landscape provides a rich context for examining how play influences public space utilization and social interactions.

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Frankenberger Park is a well-loved green space in the heart of the neighbourhood, offering a serene environment for relaxation and recreation. It is a favourite spot for families, children, and individuals seeking a peaceful escape from the urban bustle. The park features lush lawns, mature trees, and well-maintained pathways, providing ample opportunities for walking, jogging, and picnicking. Playgrounds and sports facilities cater to the needs of younger residents and active individuals, making it a lively area throughout the day.

Neumarkt, another key public space in the neighbourhood, serves as a central gathering point for community events and markets. It is a bustling square surrounded by cafes, restaurants, and shops, creating a vibrant atmosphere where residents and visitors can socialize and enjoy the local amenities. The square often hosts cultural events, markets, and festivals, reflecting the neighbourhood's strong community spirit and diverse cultural landscape.

One of the notable features of the Frankenberger Neighbourhood is the seamless connection between its public spaces. As seen on the maps, parks and public areas are well-integrated, creating a cohesive network of green and communal spaces (Figure 1 and Figure 2). This connectivity enhances the walkability of the neighbourhood, encouraging residents to explore and engage with different areas. The integration of parks, squares, and cultural facilities fosters a sense of community and belonging, promoting active participation and ownership among residents.

Figure 1. Public Space Map

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Figure 2. Green Space Map

The behavioural map of Frankenberger Park (Figure 3) reveals a lively environment where a variety of activities take place, such as dancing, playing music, picnicking, and sports. The park offers a variety of sensory experiences, including activities such as watching kids, walking, slacklining, playing frisbee, eating ice cream, sitting on the stairs, chatting, sitting on the grass, playing in the playground, playing football, outdoor art and painting, group fitness classes, picnic parties, dog walking, dancing, mind-body exercises, playing guitar and singing, and playing basketball. These activities foster positive interactions across diverse age groups, creating a vibrant community atmosphere. In Neumarkt, activities such as sitting on the bench, sitting at the card tables, and chatting while drinking, children playing, families chatting, and playing table tennis are observed.

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Figure 3. The GIS behaviour map of Frankenberger Park 24.7.23, 5-5.30 pm.

Frankenberger Park combines recreational and historical elements to create an engaging environment for visitors. People of all ages engage in different activities, personalizing their spaces within the park, and creatively using natural materials for play equipment. The playground design takes advantage of the park's natural slope, encouraging social interaction among families and seamlessly connecting the play area to the park's historical surroundings. Situated within this park is a historic water castle, renovated and transformed into a cultural centre, thereby enhancing the area's aesthetic appeal and cultural significance. The castle serves as a venue for a wide range of cultural events and activities, among which the "slide in the pocket of the castle" stands out as a distinctive feature that adds a playful and adventurous dimension to the visitor experience. This blend of historical preservation and contemporary cultural programming attracts a diverse audience interested in both leisure activities and intellectual engagement, cementing Frankenberger Park's reputation as a revered destination for cultural enrichment and relaxation alike.

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Figure 4. People are engaging in diverse activities

Figure 5. Children are playing and families nearby.

In Figures 4 and 5, the diverse activities and playful interactions depicted underscore the multifaceted nature of public space engagement. Figure 4 illustrates a spectrum of activities, suggesting a dynamic use of the space by individuals engaging in varied pursuits such as reading, socializing, and exercising. This diversity not only reflects the inclusive design of the public space but also highlights its role as a communal hub accommodating different preferences and behaviours. Conversely, Figure 5 focuses on children engaged in play, with families nearby, emphasizing the space's function in fostering intergenerational interactions and recreational opportunities. The presence of children at play indicates a welcoming environment conducive to family activities, promoting social cohesion and a sense of belonging among community members. Together, these figures illustrate how thoughtful design and inclusivity in public spaces can cater to a range of needs and activities, enhancing urban liveability and community well-being.

Figure 6. Park with a bookshelf and benches

Figure 7. A drink car with seated patrons.

Figure 6 depicts a park scene featuring a bookshelf and benches, showcasing a deliberate integration of amenities that encourage intellectual engagement and relaxation within the public realm. The presence of a bookshelf suggests an initiative to promote literacy and cultural

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enrichment in the park environment, providing visitors with opportunities to read and exchange books freely. This amenity not only enhances the park's functionality as a space for quiet contemplation and learning but also fosters a sense of community through shared access to literature. In contrast, Figure 7 portrays a drink cart with seated patrons, illustrating the park's adaptation to accommodate social gatherings and leisure activities. The presence of a refreshment service encourages social interaction and conviviality among visitors, transforming the park into a social hub where individuals can relax, socialize, and enjoy refreshments in a casual outdoor setting. Together, these figures highlight the park's versatility in catering to both intellectual pursuits and social interactions, underscoring its role as a multifaceted public space that enhances community engagement and quality of life.

6. Designing for Play: Enhancing Public Spaces through Active Participation

The privatization of public spaces often results in environments that neglect user preferences and lack adaptability, diminishing people's sense of connection and ownership. In contrast, play theory advocates for active participation, prioritizing user experiences and engagement in design and management decisions. Active involvement is pivotal in developing public spaces, necessitating an understanding of diverse community needs, preferences, and behaviours (Madanipour, 1996). Engaging potential users in the design process empowers designers to align spaces with expectations and purposes (Shaftoe, 2008), ensuring they cater to various demographics and activities (Canter, 1974; Whyte, 1980). Consequently, public spaces seamlessly integrate with play activities, creating vibrant environments that reflect collective aspirations (Shaftoe, 2008).

The role of engagement extends beyond design, shaping urban environments that address residents' diverse needs. Active community involvement ensures public spaces resonate with the desires and aspirations of those using them. This participatory approach fosters inclusivity and vibrancy, aligning with play theory's emphasis on interactive and participatory dimensions within societal norms (Bateson, 1987).

In urban settings, play emerges as a response to life's uncertainties and tensions, paralleling participatory design where residents engage in shaping their environment to address real-life challenges. Play promotes interactive engagement and awareness among participants, while participatory design builds community by involving residents in decision-making, bridging differences and fostering shared ownership (Stevens, 2007).

Frankenberger Park and Neumarkt provide compelling examples. These spaces illustrate how tactile engagement and participatory design principles enhance urban environments. Residents actively shape and interact with these spaces, fostering immediate, reciprocal transformations that encourage exploration and play (Stevens, 2007). This interconnected relationship between play and participation transforms urban landscapes into interactive playgrounds rather than static stages. These are the benefits of incorporating play theory into participatory design for public spaces with references:

Enhanced Community Engagement: Increased community involvement leads to more inclusive and representative designs (Stevens, 2007; Boano, & Talocci, 2014).

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Fostering Creativity and Imagination: Public spaces become more innovative and unique, reflecting the diverse ideas of the community (Bateson, 1987; Lefavre & Döll, 2007).

Creating a Sense of Ownership: People feel a deeper connection to and responsibility for the spaces they help design (Stevens, 2007).

Promoting Social Interaction: Enhanced social cohesion and a sense of community develop, leading to increased usage and enjoyment of public spaces (Simmel, 1950; Shaftoe, 2008).

Fostering Inclusivity: Public spaces become more welcoming and accessible to all community members (Mumford, 1996).

Breaking Down Barriers: A more equitable and respectful dialogue among community members results in designs that reflect a broader range of needs and preferences (Simmel, 1950; Shaftoe, 2008).

Enabling Risk-Taking: Public spaces become more dynamic and innovative, with the potential for unique and exciting features (Stevens, 2007).

Strengthening the Sense of Place: Public spaces become distinct and memorable, fostering a sense of pride and attachment among residents (Mumford, 1996).

Emphasizing Playful Elements: Public spaces become more enjoyable and attractive, inviting residents to engage in creative and recreational activities (Bateson, 1987; Donoff, & Bridgman, 2017).

Improving Well-Being: Public spaces that prioritize well-being contribute to the physical and mental health of the community, fostering a happier and more resilient urban population (Maslow, 1943; Mahdjoubi, & Spencer, 2015).

In conclusion, play theory and participatory design share common principles related to the dynamic and participatory nature of urban life. Both emphasize the importance of adhering to rules and constraints, fostering social interaction, and transforming urban spaces into places of creativity and community. When applied together, play theory can inform participatory design processes, enriching the public spaces within cities and making them more inclusive, engaging, and responsive to the needs and desires of their inhabitants.

7. Conclusion

In the realm of city planning, public spaces are envisioned as inclusive hubs of accessibility and community, embodying the true essence of "public." Designed to be places where residents feel a sense of ownership and connection, these spaces foster a sense of belonging and shared experiences among city residents (Madanipour, 2010). This ownership is crucial for creating vibrant and dynamic urban environments, as demonstrated by the Frankenger Neighbourhood, particularly in Frankenger Park and Neumarkt, where residents actively engage with and transform their surroundings. Understanding and encouraging this sense of ownership is key to meeting a wide spectrum of needs and preferences in urban design.

Central to this concept is the idea of play, which emerges as a transformative force in urban design, particularly evident in research conducted within Frankenger Park and Neumarkt.

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By integrating play theory into the design process, we not only acknowledge the importance of active participation but also encourage social interaction and creativity in public spaces. This approach revitalizes urban areas by offering opportunities for spontaneous engagement and personal expression (Lefavre & Döll, 2007).

Frankenberger Park and Neumarkt serve as living laboratories, showcasing how playful design principles can redefine boundaries and enhance social dynamics. Through direct observations and behaviour mapping, residents actively engage with and transform their surroundings, creating inclusive and dynamic public environments. This case study underscores the role of play in fostering community involvement and reimagining the use of public spaces as vibrant centres of social interaction.

This article contributes significantly to urban design theory by advocating for a holistic understanding of public spaces and emphasizing the transformative potential of play theory. By presenting examples from Frankenberger and beyond, it illustrates how playful engagement can enhance accessibility, adaptability, and inclusivity in urban settings. The integration of play theory empowers individuals to shape the evolution of their urban environments, promoting a sense of ownership and deepening the connection between people and place (Carr & Fraser, 1993). It emphasizes the importance of considering the diverse needs and preferences of individuals and communities in the design process, promoting active participation, and owning public spaces.

In conclusion, embracing play as a fundamental element of urban design leads to the creation of lively and adaptable cities that reflect the diverse needs and experiences of their communities. This approach exemplifies how play can transform public spaces into dynamic hubs of creativity and social interaction, fostering a sense of ownership among residents. By encouraging active participation and personal expression, urban environments become more inclusive and engaging for all.

Information Note:

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